

IMPROVING THE INVESTMENT ACTIVITIES OF INSURANCE COMPANIES

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Annotation

This article analyzes the investment indicators of insurance companies operating in the insurance market of Uzbekistan, and explores the possibilities of increasing the financial stability of insurance companies by improving the efficiency of their investment activities.

Keywords:

❖ insurance market, insurance organization, investment flow, investment environment, investment attractive-ness, investment law.

Introduction.

In Uzbekistan’s insurance market, there are 38 insurance organizations whose primary goal is to serve the interests of policyholders in a healthy competitive environment by providing high-quality insurance services. Additionally, they aim to engage in domestic investment activities within the legal framework using temporarily accumulated insurance reserves. By effectively utilizing insurance premiums collected for assumed insurance liabilities, even temporarily, insurance organizations can enhance their financial stability. To achieve this, the legal foundations of investment activities for insurance organizations have been established. Investment targets have been specified for insurance companies, allowing them to direct temporarily accumulated reserve funds and their own financial assets as internal investments.

Literature review.

Improving the investment activities of insurance companies is crucial for the stable development of the economy and has been

thoroughly analyzed by numerous scholars and researchers. Research on developing the insurance sector in Uzbekistan, in particular, has focused on enhancing the investment potential of insurance companies, ensuring their financial stability, and advancing their investment activities to an international level.

Among Uzbek scholars, Abdullayev emphasizes in his research the importance of diversifying the investment portfolio for insurance companies and strengthening connections with international financial markets. He believes that expanding the investment activities of insurance companies can not only improve their financial position but also positively impact the economy as a whole. This, in turn, contributes to enhancing the investment environment in the country and advancing the insurance sector to the international level.

Additionally, Sh.Boymurodov highlights the importance of risk management in the investment activities of insurance companies in his research. He emphasizes the need for insurance companies to use modern investment technologies and analyze risks to

ensure their financial stability. According to Boymurodov, proper risk management serves as a foundation for the long-term success of insurance companies and enhances their competitiveness.

Foreign sources also examine this issue in depth. For example, Mishkin and Eakins analyze how the investment activities of insurance companies integrate with global financial markets in their research. They review the investment strategies of international insurance companies, exploring how these companies can reduce risks and ensure financial stability by diversifying their portfolios. They argue that insurance companies can succeed in the global financial market by carefully planning their investment strategies.

The literature review above demonstrates that strategic planning, diversification, risk management, and integration with international financial markets play a crucial role in improving the investment activities of insurance companies. Additionally, by applying national legislation and modern technologies, insurance companies can advance their approach to investments.

Research methodology.

This research employs widely used scientific research methods. To study the topic effectively, both deductive and inductive methods were utilized, moving from general to specific concepts and vice versa, respectively. The abstract-logical thinking method is particularly useful in systematically analyzing the process. Throughout the scientific analysis, methods such as observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, synthesis, and analysis were extensively applied.

Analysis and results.

In foreign countries, two main approaches to state regulation of investment policy exist, revealing the role and influence of the state in investment activities and in setting tariff rates. The first approach is the American model, where the primary activity may incur losses, but these losses can be offset by income from investment activities. The second approach is the European model, in which the core insurance activities must generate profits, independent of investment income. Practical observations show that long-term investments tend to generate more profit than medium- and short-term investments in insurance portfolios. [1]”

Table 1

Characteristics of Government Oversight of Investment Activities of Insurance Companies in Foreign Countries (Ernst & Young, 2023) [2]

USA	A certain portion of income is invested within the state’s territory. Investment conditions are established according to specified regulations. The composition of average assets is determined. Insurance companies provide investment loans to enterprises in industrial sectors for periods of 15-20 years.
GREAT BRITAIN	Rules for allocating financial resources are established. The average composition of life insurance assets is determined. A government investment policy program is in place. Continuous monitoring of the investment portfolio’s value is conducted.
GERMANY	A law governing the placement of insurance company serves is in effect. Principles of investment apply (safety, profitability, liquidity, diversification, etc.). Investment forms and related restrictions are established. Assets are transferred to reliable management.

Long-term investments include real estate transactions, while medium and short-term investments include stocks, securities, bank deposits, and temporary funds in the company's accounts. However, it should be noted that although long-term investments generate more income, medium and short-term investments are considered liquid when payment obligations arise.

Based on the experience of developed countries, the ongoing measures to further improve insurance activities in Uzbekistan are creating necessary conditions for the rapid development of the insurance market. The government plays a leading role in ensuring that the country's insurance companies meet international standards and become competitive in the industry. The adoption of a series of regulatory documents related to insurance activities is improving the quality of insurance services and building greater public trust in the sector [3].

The growth of investment income enables insurance companies to secure necessary reserves, attract customers, and actively develop the insurance sector, while also allowing for a confident review of tariff policies aimed at dominating the insurance market. Investment income enables insurance companies to discount reserves, cover their liabilities, and increase the funds of policyholders in savings and insurance “accumulators”.

The amount of investment income depends on the reliability and effectiveness of the asset placement, the company's balanced investment policy, and the investment timeframes.

One of the key tasks in organizing the activities of insurers is properly assessing risk. It is evident that due to changes in the external economic environment, insurance companies must effectively establish risk management mechanisms. In today's context, insurance companies should develop specific regulatory and legal documents for managing various

risks, including investment, operational, and financial risks.

There are several advantages to using the mechanism of managing investment risks in insurance:

1. Insurance as an effective risk management tool allows for the identification, analysis, and assessment of risks, as well as compensating for losses incurred from those risks.

2. Insurance is more affordable and convenient compared to other risk management methods.

3. The widespread use of modern information technologies, the digitization of the insurance market, and improved consumer confidence lead to greater efficiency in the sector, as well as the alignment of the national insurance market with international standards [4].

Additionally, the creation of new jobs in regions, increased competition, and enhanced business reliability not only stimulate the growth of the insurance services sector but also contribute to the development of related industries and expand investment opportunities in various sectors.

Currently, various insurance companies operate in Uzbekistan's insurance market. To make effective management decisions, insurance companies can be grouped and classified based on several characteristics. The choice of classification criteria and the number of groups depend on the specific research objectives. Classification of the insurance market is the starting point for both macro and micro-level analysis. Therefore, several classification methods are widely accepted in insurance theory and practice.

By studying each classification method, it is possible to analyze the investment activities of insurance companies and explore the investment portfolio policies for each classification group, as the structure of investment portfolios may significantly differ between groups.

Moreover, depending on their specialization, the investment policies of insurance companies in different groups can vary significantly. For example, contracts for certain types of insurance are usually concluded for one year. The insurance company receives the premiums within this period, indicating that the investment policy should be short-term. In most cases, if the company makes long-term investments, it could face high-risk levels in terms of liquidity. As a result, temporary investment disruptions may occur. Therefore, it is more appropriate for insurance companies to allocate their financial resources to high-liquid, medium, and short-term assets. This ensures that the company can meet its financial needs or promptly fulfill insurance payments when required [5].

In 2023, insurance companies still directed the majority of their investment activities towards bank deposits, which indicates that Uzbekistan's securities market has not yet reached an advanced stage of development. To improve, Uzbekistan's insurance companies need to enhance the legal framework of their investment activities by introducing standards that align with modern requirements.

As of October 1, 2022, according to the data from the Central Securities Depository, the volume of shares issued by professional participants of the Uzbek insurance market amounted to 1.903 trillion sums. By the end of 2022, the total authorized capital of insurance companies was 1.884 trillion sums. On November 15, 2023, “Uzbekinvest” export-import insurance company announced a roadshow to conduct the initial public offering (IPO) of shares at the “Tashkent” Republic Stock Exchange, where a series of meetings with potential investors were planned. As part of this IPO placement, “Uzbekinvest” insurance company issued 14.1 million preferential shares, which represents 5% of the company's authorized capital. The guaranteed fixed dividend income from these shares is set at “the

refinancing rate of the Central Bank of Uzbekistan + 10%,” which currently corresponds to an annual rate of 24%.

Improving business management in insurance companies and ensuring their active participation in the wide-ranging reforms being carried out in the country is a priority. Specifically, the transition of insurance companies from limited liability companies to joint-stock companies is highlighted in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan 730, which defines the organization of professional participants in the insurance market and the procedure for their state registration. According to article 39 of the decision, insurance companies (and reinsurers) will be established in the form of joint-stock companies [6].

According to the analysis of the volume and number of shares issued by Uzbek insurance companies as joint-stock companies, 44 insurance companies have 1.9 trillion sums worth of shares in the Central Securities Depository. However, the most recent significant fact regarding the activity of AgroInvest Insurance Joint-Stock Company was announced on September 5, 2016. Due to the company's regulator being called in, the company has not provided insurance services in recent years. The Corporate Information Portal announced only one significant fact regarding the activity of Fortuna Insurance Joint-Stock Company, which was the issuance of 15 billion sums in shares with a nominal value of 1,000 sums in a closed subscription process on April 6, 2022 [7].

According to the analysis of tables, Kapital Insurance and Universal Insurance joint-stock companies issued shares with a nominal value of one kopeck. In addition, Kafolat Insurance, Imkon Insurance, TRUST-INSURANCE, and UNIPOLIS Insurance companies issued shares with a nominal value of 1 sum to form their authorized capital.

According to current legislation, the maximum nominal value of shares is set at

5,000 sums, but issuing shares at such a low nominal value has created specific challenges in corporate financial calculations and shareholder general assembly minutes. Although insurance companies have been transformed into joint-stock companies as per legal requirements, the majority of them have placed their shares in a closed subscription process. This situation can also be seen as a natural condition for newly established joint-stock companies since such companies typically place their shares in an initial closed subscription [8].

Conclusion and Recommendations.

The majority of the population in Uzbekistan views the securities market with distrust and skepticism. The financial literacy of the population in Uzbekistan is insufficient, which is reflected in people's inability to develop long-term financial plans, save money effectively, and take responsibility for their future. Experts believe that developing a special program to improve the financial literacy level of the population would be beneficial.

The securities market plays an important role in the economic development of most countries. Underestimating the role of the stock market can be costly for the state because economic crises often begin in the stock markets and then spread to other sectors of the economy. A clear example of this is the collapse

of the New York Stock Exchange in 1929, which later turned into the 1929–1934 global economic crisis known as the “Great Depression”.

However, in rapidly developing countries, including Uzbekistan, the primary function of the securities market is savings mobilization. Through the securities market, temporarily idle financial resources, including those of individuals, businesses, and organizations, as well as state funds, are mobilized and directed towards financing the development of various sectors of the national economy.

In developed countries, there are standards for the placement of insurance companies' assets, the maximum and minimum quotas for insurance reserves, and a list of assets covering insurance reserves. These developed standards are regulated based on the level of economic development, the state of financial markets, and national traditions. The investment directions of insurance companies are specified separately for life insurance and other general insurance sectors.

In the European Union, the United Kingdom, and the United States, the responsibility for regulating the insurance market is divided between the state, local, and regional authorities to a certain extent. In the U.S., each state has its own independent regulatory bodies for the insurance sector.

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